

PHILOLOGY

NONVERBAL COMMUNICATION AND LITERARY TRANSLATION PROBLEMS IN LANGUAGES WITH DIFFERENT SYSTEMS

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Abstract

This article explores the challenges inherent in translating literary works between languages with distinct cultural and non-verbal communication systems. It emphasizes the importance of accurately conveying cultural and metaphorical elements from the source language to the target audience. The author highlights that translation is not merely a linguistic act but a cultural process, wherein understanding the nuances of the source culture is vital for effective communication. Symbolic gestures and culturally specific metaphors pose unique translation issues. These require adaptation to ensure that the target audience comprehends the intended message. The article discusses methods such as generalization and component analysis, as outlined by theorists like J. B. Casagrande and P. Newmark. These approaches either emphasize cultural preservation or prioritize message clarity by minimizing cultural specificity.

Examples from translations of Uzbek literary works into English demonstrate how non-verbal nuances and cultural meanings are often diluted or omitted, leading to a loss of stylistic and contextual richness. Translators must develop a deep understanding of both linguistic and cultural dimensions to bridge gaps and maintain the essence of the original text. The article underscores the translator's role as a cultural mediator, advocating for careful consideration of cultural elements to enrich the target text while maintaining its authenticity and accessibility.

Keywords: Non-verbal communication, literary translation, cultural differences, source language, target language, translation challenges, symbolic gestures, metaphorical expressions.

According to some academics, a variety of symbolic gestures that are either nonexistent or have a different meaning in the linguistic culture may provide unique translation issues when translating the source language. Translating different metaphorical and figurative terms presents similar challenges. The translator offers more details, employs a different (Russian) word with a comparable meaning, or clarifies the metaphorical meaning of English idioms in order to guarantee accurate comprehension of the translation of such an expression.

Also, in literary translation, the main goal of the translator is to convey the original message to the receptor of the target language. Understanding the message means interpreting it on the basis of the necessary knowledge. If such knowledge is lacking due to differences in cultural or non-verbal means, it must be supplemented or compensated. In the translation of non-verbal means, cultural characteristics affect how linguistic units are used and understood. Culture finds its expression in and through language. An extra-linguistic theory of translation must also include the cultural aspect. Translating from one culture to another is equivalent to translating from one language to another.

It is necessary to justify the focus on the cultural aspect of translation, as opposed to the linguistic and extra-linguistic aspects. This aspect of translation is clearly reflected in the formula of J. B. Casagrande: "Not languages, but cultures are translated"

It is known that the ability to understand and overcome cultural differences of the receptors in the perception of the original textual message in the translated text helps the translator. Even within the same culture, there are many subcultures and divisions, and these people

are accustomed to other people speaking, acting and believing differently from themselves, which is reflected in the specific stereotypes of the participants in the communication.

For example, we can say that a Russian reader can easily accept that Bulgarians nod in agreement, that drivers in Britain drive on the left side of the road, or that cows are sacred animals in India. A person born in a tropical country, where summer is not the most pleasant season of the year, reading Shakespeare's sonnet "Shall I compare thee to a summer's day," may not understand what the poet meant, and may consider it flattering. In his culture, summer looks different. "I even suggest that the phrase 'as white as snow' be clearly understood in the translation by someone who has never seen a snowdrift, so that he can guess that it is something very white.

Taking this aspect into account, it is worth noting, that the same or similar extra-linguistic aspect is also found in works of fiction translated from Uzbek into English. For example, in the translation of Erkin A'zam's story "The Writer" by A'zam Obidov, the semantic and contextual features of non-verbal communication tools were often implemented in the translated text using the generalization method. As a result, the stylistic coloring of the contextual meaning in the original text also lost its effectiveness to a certain extent:

Muharririmiz bergan nomdan mamnun oshpaz-qorovul "tushundim-tushundim" degandek sirdoshlarcha bosh qimtib, oshxona tomon zippilaydi. [<https://n.ziyouz.com/portal-haqida/xarita/uzbek-nasri/erkin-a-zam-1950/erkin-a-zam-yozuvchi-hikoya>]

In Uzbek, *sirdosh* - means the people who confide in each other, tell secrets to each other, sympathizers,

and the word *bosh qimtimoq* means "qismoq", "silkitmoq", "qimirlatmoq".

Translation of the text: *The cook, pleased with the name our editor gave him; nods: "understood" and hurries to the kitchen to prepare food for them. "To nod"- If you nod, you move your head downwards and upwards to show that you are answering "yes" to a question, or to show agreement, understanding, or approval.* [<https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/nod>]

Translation text: The cook, pleased with the name our editor gave him; nods: "understood" and hurries to the kitchen to prepare food for them. "To nod"- If you nod, you move your head downwards and upwards to show that you are answering "yes" to a question, or to show agreement, understanding, or approval. [<https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/nod>]

In this case, the inclusion of the nonverbal communicative tool (*sirdoshlar*) in the *sirdoshlar* *tushindim-tushindim* expression in the general meaning of the verb (*tushindim*) and the repeated verb form (*tushindim-tushindim*) in the general verb structure and translation reduced the semantic coloring and impact of the context, as a result, the pragmatic essence of the text was not perceived in the translated text. In particular, the reason for the generalization of the phrase "intimately", which has English equivalents such as "intimately", "confidently", "secretly", "solely" can be considered that none of these equivalents can cover the semantic-contextual meaning expressed by the word in the Uzbek text. Because, intimately - closely in a personal or sexual way, in a very detailed way. [<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/intimately>]

You have to be willing to get to know yourself and your partner intimately.

[<https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/intimate>]

Confidently-in a way that shows you are certain of your abilities or have trust in people, plans, or the future. [<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/confidently>]

Secretly- in a way that people do not know or are not told about. [<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/secretly>]

Solely- only and not involving anyone or anything else. [<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/solely>]

After all, the purpose of communication is to send a message with the intention of informing, inspiring or asking questions so that the message is fully understood by the recipient. Face-to-face communication is much more than just an exchange of words. Facial expressions, hand gestures, body position, eye contact, even silence ... all of these constantly send messages about our relationships, feelings, and state.

Translation theory recognizes a number of problems associated with the theory of interaction. Nonverbal means, language, and culture are considered to be closely related to each other, and this coherence must be taken into account both lexically and pragmatically. In particular, considering the translation of cultural words and concepts, Newmark proposed two contrasting methods: transfer and component analysis. In his opinion, transfer suggests bringing "national color," that is, culture, directly into the translated text while

preserving cultural names and concepts. It has been argued that the presence of these tools in the translated text is a reasonable solution for culturally sensitive readers, while this method, in turn, can cause problems for the general readership and limit understanding in some respects. The importance of the translation process in communication led P. Newmark to propose component analysis, which he describes as "the most appropriate translation process that excludes culture and emphasizes the message."

As P. Newmark noted, perhaps the most important observation of communication theorists for translators is the recognition that every act of communication has three dimensions: the speaker (author), the message and the audience. Awareness of the nature of these components in the translation process serves to enrich the skills and linguistic knowledge of translators and ensure the naturalness of the translation of the text. When these three dimensions are combined, communication is effective. P. Newmark defined culture as "the way of life characteristic of a society that uses a particular language as a means of expression and its manifestation", thereby recognizing that each language group has its own cultural characteristics. He also introduced the concept of "cultural words", which are difficult for readers to understand, and argued that translation strategies for this type of concept depend on the specific type of text, the requirements of readers and clients, and the preservation of cultural words and non-verbal means in the text in translation.

It is known, that in the translation process, in order to find a translation of a word, it is necessary to compare the semantic properties of several words in a synonymic series and select the most suitable option.

In conclusion, it can be said that there are a number of difficulties encountered in translating non-verbal communicative means from one language to another in the translation of literary works written in different systematic languages, and in most cases they are neutralized or omitted altogether in direct and indirect translations. Lexicographic analysis of non-verbal means shows that although bilingual dictionaries do not provide equivalents in the translation of non-verbal communicative means, the presence of lexical units expressing exactly this meaning in monolingual explanatory dictionaries, and the use of these words in the translation text requires additional work from the translator, a correct understanding of the pragmatic aspect of the original text and its correct expression in the language being translated.

References

1. V.N. Komissarov "Language and Culture in Translation: Competitors or Collaborators?", TTR: traduction, terminologie, rédaction, vol. 4, №1, 1991, p. 46
2. В.А. Зайцева «Электронный учебно-методический комплекс по учебной дисциплине «Перевод и межкультурная коммуникация» для специальности «Современные иностранные языки (перевод)» 1 – 21 06 01-02, 2014, 13-стр.
3. В.А. Зайцева «Электронный учебно-методический комплекс по учебной дисциплине «Перевод и межкультурная коммуникация» для специальности «Современные иностранные языки (перевод)» 1 – 21 06 01-02, 2014, 5-стр